

UNDERSTANDING WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURIAL INNOVATION: THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL NETWORKS, TRUST, AND CULTURAL CONTEXT

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Abstract

The increasing presence of women business owners, described by Baker et al. (1997, p. 221) as a "gender revolution in business ownership", has been described as a significant driver of social and economic development. However, research in entrepreneurship indicates that women entrepreneurs are generally less oriented toward innovation compared to their male counterparts. Since innovation is closely linked to the establishment of high-performing firms, it plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth, job creation, and improvements in societal well-being. As such, it represents a vital mechanism through which entrepreneurs can achieve broader societal impact. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition that the innovative performance of a firm is undertaken in a social context and shaped by interactions and the exchange of knowledge among diverse social actors. Consequently, social networks are essential in providing entrepreneurs with access to resources, such as knowledge and ideas, that enhance their innovative capacity.

This study argues that sociological factors are key to understanding differences in levels of innovation among entrepreneurs. It focuses specifically on the influence of social networks on women entrepreneurs' innovation. Additionally, it explores the role of national values—particularly trust—and national culture, both as determinants of innovation and as moderating factors in the relationship between social networks and women's entrepreneurial behaviour.

The analysis utilizes individual-level data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) covering 46 countries in 2020 (with nearly 140,000 observations). This data is combined with national-level cultural context data from GEM's National Expert Survey (NES) and trust data from the World Values Survey (WVS). The findings reveal that social networks positively influence women's entrepreneurial innovation. Public sphere networks have a significant positive effect on innovation, whereas private sphere networks show variable impacts. Trust is identified as a critical national value that directly fosters innovation among women entrepreneurs. Trust not only fosters innovation among women entrepreneurs but also moderates the relationship between social networks and women entrepreneurial innovation. Furthermore, cultural factors have a significant impact on the innovative behaviour of women entrepreneurs' innovativeness. These findings also provide valuable insights into how the innovativeness of women entrepreneurs can be supported within specific cultural contexts.

Keywords: Women entrepreneur, Entrepreneurial Innovation, Social Networks, Cultural Context.